

PARENTAL SUPPORT AND PRINCIPAL'S ADMINISTRATIVE EFFECTIVENESS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN BAYELSA STATE, NIGERIA

BY

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Abstract

The research examined the relationship between parental support and principal's administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa State. The total population of the study comprised of 2,350 participants from 189 secondary schools in Bayelsa State. This was made up of 189 public secondary school principals and 2,161 teachers. Correlational survey design was used for the study. The sample size of the study was 235 participants which is 10% of 2,350. From the 235, 48 were principals while 187 were teachers. The researcher used stratified random sampling technique in selecting the principals and teachers in the public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Questionnaires titled "Parental Support Questionnaire (PSQ)" and "Principals' Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (PAEQ)" were used as the research instrument. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistical tool was used to test the two (2) hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that when parents are involved in developing school policies and collaborating with the principals in the decision-making process, it promotes accountability and transparency in school administration and helps the principals maintain a positive and supportive school environment. It was recommended that principals should actively promote and support the functioning of Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs). By making sure all parents are involved in school decision-making and governance processes so that schools can benefit from their insights and contributions, which can enhance the effectiveness of school administration, this will also help for the smooth administration of schools in Bayelsa State.

Keywords: Parental Support, Principal, Administrative Effectiveness, Secondary Schools.

Introduction

Parental involvement in school administration is widely regarded as the bedrock for academic achievement and effective school administrative management. In secondary schools, the commitment and support of parents not only help student outcomes but also significantly influence the administrative effectiveness of school heads (Principals). This is particularly important in Bayelsa State, where principals face various challenges, including limited and scarce resources, and socio-cultural factors that affect school operations. According to Akinfolarin et al. (2016), parental support can lead to improved academic performance and discipline, both of which are critical for school management. Parental support comes in different forms, such

as participating in school meetings, volunteering, and providing resources for extracurricular activities, all of which contribute to an organized and efficient school system (Adeyemo & Babajide, 2021).

The activeness of a principal's administration is closely related to the level of support they receive from parents. Principals who enjoy strong support from the community and parents can better implement policies, manage resources, and foster a positive school climate. Ejiogun et al. (2018) observed that principals who had high levels of parental support reported fewer issues with student discipline and higher teacher morale, leading to an overall improvement in administrative effectiveness.

Studies by Ige (2019) and Alade and Babalola (2023) strongly maintained that when parents actively support school initiatives, principals can lead with greater authority and confidence, knowing they have the backing of the school community. This collaboration is crucial in addressing complex issues such as attendance, discipline, and academic excellence, which require a united front from both school and home environments. Parental support also contributes to principals' emotional and psychological well-being, enabling them to perform their duties more effectively. When principals feel supported by parents, they are less likely to experience burnout and more likely to exhibit resilience and commitment to school improvement efforts (Ajayi et al.,2022).

Moreover, parental support often metamorphoses into increased resource availability and community backing for the school. Principals who enjoy consistent support from parents are more empowered to execute developmental projects, address students' needs, and ensure a safe and conducive learning environment. This collaboration not only enhances student academic performance but also boosts staff morale, as the school community works together toward common goals. Ultimately, when parents are actively engaged, it solidifies the principal's authority and amplifies their ability to lead with impact and efficiency. As I always affirm, "The strength of a school's leadership is deeply rooted in the support it receives from its parents (Obi, 2024).

The influence of parental support on school administration extends beyond resource provision; it also encourages transparency and accountability. According to Bello and Fagbamila (2020), parents who are involved and invested in the school are more likely to advocate for transparent practices and support principals in their administrative duties, creating a stable and effective administrative structure. By establishing clear communication channels and

encouraging trust between parents and the school administration.

Statement of the Problem

There is a major outcry between parents and principals' administration that leads to lack of cooperation between principals of secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Consequently, these issues contribute to inefficiencies in the administration of secondary schools, affecting their ability to achieve set objectives and deliver quality education. A harmonious relationship between parents and school administrators is critical to fostering a positive school climate, enhancing stakeholder trust, and ensuring the smooth functioning of secondary schools. Lack of collaboration fosters mistrust between principals, parents, and other stakeholders, undermining the school climate and creating organizational disharmony. However, in Bayelsa State, the persistent lack of parental support for administrative processes has aggravated the challenges such as resource constraints, inadequate discipline enforcement, and ineffective communication. These factors not only hinder the ability of principals to carry out their administrative roles effectively but also abate the quality of education provided.

This study therefore, aim to investigate the impact of parental support and principal's administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa state.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to investigate the relationship between parental support and principals' administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa State. The specific objectives of the study were follows:

1. Examine how parental evaluation of principals relate to principals' administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

2. Examine how parental support in decision-making relates to principals' administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

To address the objectives of this research, the following research questions was addressed:

1. How does parental evaluation of principals relate to principals' administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa State?
2. How does parental support in decision-making relate to principals' administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

Based on the research questions, the following hypotheses were used and tested at .05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between parental evaluation of principals and principals' administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa State
2. There is no significant relationship or difference between parental support in decision-making and principals' administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Significance of the Study

This study will be of immense benefits to improve educational outcomes and school management, it will help to understand how parental involvement impacts administrative effectiveness and provides valuable insights for school educators, leaders, and policymakers. Also aiming to improve a supportive and productive school environment. This study highlights the importance of parental support as a vital component in effective school administration, showing that when parents are actively involved, principals can better enforce

discipline, manage resources, and achieve academic goals.

For policymakers, this study emphasizes the necessity of creating frameworks that facilitate parental participation in school affairs, regardless of socio-economic barriers. Such frameworks can lead to greater equity in education by ensuring that all parents have equal opportunities to contribute to their children's education. For school administrators, the study will expose practical benefits of fostering parental involvement. By understanding the role that parents play in the educational process and how their participation can support school management, principals can engineer more effective strategies for engaging parents and strengthening school-community partnerships. This, in turn, can lead to more effective resource management, and decision-making policy implementation in schools. Finally, this study will be of immense benefits to parents and students. It will provide parents with evidence of the positive impact they can have on their children's academic success and the school environment as a whole

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

Parental Involvement Theory (By Henderson &Berla, 1994)

This theory provides a framework for understanding the important role parents participate in the personal and academic development of their children in a school setting. Rooted in educational psychology, this theory emphasizes that active parental involvement in secondary education has positive impact on student academic achievement, behavior, and motivation. According to Epstein's (2011) model, parental involvement encompasses various dimensions, including parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making, and collaborating with the community. These activities strengthen the

relationship between home and school, creating a supportive environment that facilitates learning. Studies have also shown that parental involvement is important and beneficial at all stages of education, from early childhood through adolescence. Jeynes (2016) said that children whose parents are engaged in school activities and provide educational support at home achieve better grades and have higher graduation rates. For students in secondary schools, parental engagement has been associated with improved self-discipline, motivation, and emotional well-being, as parents serve as role models and advocates for their children's academic success.

Parental Involvement Theory is central to understanding the impact of parental support on principals' administrative effectiveness in secondary schools. This theory highlights the crucial role of active parent participation in enhancing students' academic experience and overall development of school administration. When parents are fully involved, they contribute to a supportive school environment, enabling principals to put in use the policies more effectively and address students' interest generally. Increased parental involvements develop a partnership between home and school, reducing conflict, enhancing communication, and promoting the various goals. This collaboration positively influences administrative decisions, creating a stable, cooperative environment that will enhance both academic performance and school management system.

The strength of this theory encourages parents to go beyond basic involvement, actively participating in school programs, decision-making, and creating an enabling learning environment at home. Through digitalized influence and individualized consideration.

Conceptual Framework

Parental Support

Parental support is very important in the achievement of high academic standard in secondary schools; this will also enhance the learn ability of the students. According to Ceka and Murati (2016) a parent is defined as any adult who is charged with a responsibility of rearing a child, taking care and contributing towards raising their children whether biological or adopted. Parental plays a crucial role in the educational experience, development, and achievement of students in secondary schools. When parents are actively involved in their children's education, it positively changes students' behaviour, motivation, and academic performance. Parental support is of different kinds this includes; encouraging academic efforts, providing financial resources, monitoring homework, attending school functions, and maintaining effective communication with teachers and administrators. These actions create a supportive learning environment that improve students' sense of responsibility and commitment to their studies.

The acceptability of parental support significantly contributes positively to students' academic success by fostering a sense of belonging and a positive outlook on schoolwork. According to Osei-Akoto (2012), students whose parents provide both academic and emotional support are more likely to exhibit a positive attitude towards school, which in turn enhances their learning outcomes. This support is important during adolescence period marked by developmental changes and increased peer influence. Students with engaged parents tend to have higher self-esteem and better social skills, which can lead to improved academic performance and lower rates of behavioral problems. Amponsah et al. (2015) observed that students with adequate financial support for their educational needs had a clear advantage in terms of academic achievement. They argued that

when parents invest in their children's education, students are less likely to be absent and more likely to participate actively in school activities, which enhances their learning experiences.

In conclusion, parental support cannot be overemphasized to principals' administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Serious involvement from parents, through financial assistance communication, and reinforcement of school policies, furnished principals with the resources and support needed to effectively manage schools more effectively and efficiently. While challenges may arise from over-involvement, a balanced method to parental engagement drives a collaborative atmosphere that improved both school administration and student learning outcomes. As educational system is dynamic the integration of digital tools, the relationship between parents and principals will likely continue to change to meet the current trend and standard of education and also providing further opportunities for collaborative administration in secondary schools across Nigeria.

Methods

The research work employed a correlational research design. The population of the study entailed 2,350 participants from 189 secondary schools in Bayelsa State. This is made up of 189 public secondary school principals and 2,161

teachers. The sample for the study was 235 participants which is 10% of 2,350. From the 235, 48 were principals while 187 were teachers. The researcher used stratified random sampling technique in selecting the principals and teachers in the public secondary schools in Bayelsa States. A self-developed questionnaire titled "Parental Support Questionnaire (PSQ)" and "Principals' Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (PAEQ)" was used as the research instrument after being submitted and modified by the supervisor. Face and content validity instrument was established by subjecting the instrument to an expert in educational administration for screening and another who is a specialist in measurement and evaluation in the Department of Guidance and Counseling in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. To ensure that the instrument measured considerably and consistently what it is intended to measure, it was subjected to a split-half reliability test. The result gotten was correlated with the Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (r). The scores were computed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics. The researcher analyzed the demographic variables with the statistics of simple percentage while Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used in answering the research questions and hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: Does parental support in decision-making relate to principals' administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 1 - Mean and standard deviation revealing the parental support in secondary schools in Bayelsa State

S/N	Items	Means	SD	Remark
1.	Parents regularly attend school events and PTA meetings as a way of showing their unalloyed support to the school	3.11	0.32	Agreed
2.	Parents encourage and monitor their children’s academic progress at home	2.90	0.85	Disagreed
3.	Parents reinforce the school’s rules and discipline, Policies at home.	2.35	0.80	Agreed
10.	Parents actively participate in decisions related to school policies that affect their children	3.02	0.29	Agreed
11.	Parents volunteer their time and resources to support school activities and programs	2.93	0.36	Agreed
12.	Parents communicate frequently with teachers about, their child’s performance and behavior	3.13	0.60	Agreed
Grand mean		2.90	0.47	Agreed

From the data presented and analyzed in table 1, most of the respondents agreed with the statements made in item 1, 2, 4, 5 and 6 because their respective arithmetic mean was 3.11, 2.90, 3.02, 2.93 and 3.13. This showed that parents demonstrate their unweaving support by regularly attending PTA meeting and school events, also volunteer their resources and time to

support school activities and programs. On the other hand, majority of respondents disagreed with the statement made in item 3 because its mean was 2.35 (this is below the criterion mean of 2.50). This also shows that majority of parents do not hold on the school’s rules and discipline policies at home.

Research Question 2: How does parental evaluation of principals relate to principals’ administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation showing principals’ administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Bayelsa State

S/N	Items	Means	SD	Remark
	The finances, facilities, staff are managed by the principal to enhance the learning environment	3.26	0.94	Agreed
7.				
8.	The Principal introduced a positive school culture, by building respect and collaboration among staff and student	2.97	0.95	Agreed
9.	The principal regularly communicates with Students, parents, and staff about school matters, and academic performance	2.88	0.80	Agreed
10.	The principal actively involves community and the ,Parents in school activities and Programmes	2.01	0.51	Disagreed
11.	The principal effectively drives school, Policies and ensures compliance by all members of the school	2.63	0.72	Agreed
12.	The principal makes sure the school curriculum is smoothly delivered and correspond with the National standards	3.46	0.54	Agreed
Grand mean		2.86	0.74	Agreed

In the table above, item 7, 8, 9, 11 and 12 had mean values of 3.26, 2.97, 2.88, 2.63 and 3.346 respectively from the data presented. This means that most majority of respondents agreed that the principal effectively manages materials, human and financial resources which helps in the effective administration. It also showed that the

principal regularly communicates with students, staff, and parents about school activities and programmes. The statement made in item 10 had a mean value of 2.01 and reveals that most of the respondents disagreed with the statement that the principal actively involves parents and the

community in school activities and decision-making processes. This is also because the mean value of (2.01) is below the criterion mean of 2.50.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 3: Correlation analysis of the relationship between parental support in decision-making and principals' administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa State

Variables	Mean	SD	r	P-value	Remark
Parents' support in school decision-making	2.31	.414	0.66	0.16	Not Significant
Principals' administrative effectiveness	2.73	.419			

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 3 shows that there is significant relationship between parental support in school decision making and principals' administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between parental support in decision-making and principals' administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa State

Bayelsa State ($r = 0.16, p > 0.05$). The null hypothesis is hereby totally rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between parents' evaluation and principals' administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Table 4: show the Correlation analysis of the relationship between parental evaluation and principals' administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa State

Variables	Mean	SD	r	P-value	Remark
Parental evaluation	3.19	2.419	0.04	0.92	Not Significant
Principals' administrative effectiveness	2.73	.419			

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 4 shows that there is significant relationship between parental evaluation and principals' administrative effectiveness among secondary schools in Bayelsa State ($r = 0.04, p > 0.05$). The null hypothesis is hereby rejected.

developmental changes and increased peer influence. Students with engaged parents tend to have higher self-esteem and better social skills, because the child learn from the parents, since the child is closer to the parents in the adolescence period, this will enhance the academic performance of the child.

Discussions

Parental Participation in School Events and Policies

Parents' frequent attendance at school events and PTA meetings shows commitment, this is with Osei-Akoto's (2012) assertion that parental support improved students' learning outcomes and attitudes toward education. According to him, students whose parents support both emotional and academic are more likely to express a positive attitude behaviour towards school, which in turn enhances or drives their learning outcomes. This support is essential during adolescence, a period marked by

Parental Communication with Teachers

Regular parental communication between teachers about students' performance fosters or trigger accountability and positive attitudes, as noted by Adebayo and Olatunji (2016), who posited that, students with parents who monitored their academic progress and held them accountable for their performance were more likely to excel in their studies. According to him, this kind of support fosters a sense of accountability and encourages students to

maintain a high level of effort and progress in their studies.

Principal-Parent Communication

Principal effective communication and collaboration between parents helps the child to be abreast with current issues in the education sector, this is in line with the study of Adeyemi and Adu (2013), who indicated that parental engagement facilitates administrative effectiveness by fostering communication and collaboration between the school and home. To them, this type of partnership allows principals to address challenges more effectively, as parents contribute valuable feedback on student progress, behavioral concerns, and resource needs. Through consistent participation, parents can assist principals in understanding the community's educational expectations and beliefs and values, enabling them to be abreast with current information therefore, making more informed decisions.

PTA Contributions

Parents Teachers Association is pertinent because its support school management by providing financial resources for infrastructure and extracurricular activities by reducing principals' financial burdens and enhancing their focus on very important tasks, as stated by Olatunji (2014). To him, when parents actively participate in PTAs meetings, they enhance the principal's ability to manage school resources effectively. Parents can help fund extracurricular activities, infrastructure improvements, and other educational resources, thereby reducing financial strain on school administrators. This will be of immense benefits to the principal, as it will allow principals to allocate resources more effectively and concentrate on other critical administrative tasks, such as staff management, curriculum development, and student wellbeing.

Conclusion

Parental support plays a vital role in improving principals' administrative effectiveness in secondary schools as it stands to be the engine room of the school administrative system. The active involvement of parents contributes not only to a positive school environment but also supports principals in managing resources, fostering student achievement and maintaining discipline. When parents are involved in school activities or communicate openly with administrators and collaborate on school initiatives, they provide principals with essential backing that strengthens school administration and improve educational outcomes. However, achieving consistent parental involvement remains a challenge, especially in diverse socio-economic settings where resources and time may be limited. Schools that can bridge these gaps through open communication and inclusive practices are better positioned to harness the benefits of parental support, ultimately leading to more effective and resilient school leadership. By developing strong partnerships between school heads and parents, secondary schools can create an environment where both educational goals and administrative effectiveness are more reliable and readily achieved; this will help to develop the school system.

Recommendations

Based on the aim and objectives of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Schools should provide effective communication systems such as newsletters, digital platforms, and regular meetings to keep parents abreast with information. This will help to encourage parents to participate in school activities, and provide principals with valuable feedback for effective decision-making in the school system.
2. Schools should organize training like workshops and seminars to educate parents on the importance of involvement in school

activities and how it will be of a great benefit on their children's education.

3. Principals should involve parents in the development and review of school policies to create a sense of ownership and collaboration. This will help parents to contribute on the policies in the areas highly needed for educational improvement.

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